

India-America-China Triangle: A Geopolitical Perspective

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Abstract

This paper analyzes India, America and China relations with a geopolitical perspective. This paper argues that America is situated far away from China, while India shares a long boundary with China. Both America and India are threatened by China's belligerent policies. But due to geographical proximity, India's situation is far more precarious than America. From international relations' theories perspective, this paper applies the paradigm of aggressive realism, developed by John Mearsheime. This paper posits that China is hell bent upon increasing its power, unless it attains the status of a hegemon. America and India need to balance the rise of China. India should take primary responsibility to balance China due to the compulsions of geographical proximity. America should help India whole-heartedly in this endeavor since China intends to replace America as the global hegemon.

Key Words: India, aggressive realism, geopolitical, hegemon, power

This paper is based upon the theory of John Mearsheimer's (2001) aggressive realism. Its basic logic is that both India and America should be prepared to face the ascendent China. China is challenging American hegemony at every front. For India, China is the biggest challenge. Repeated crisis like Doklam and Galwan Valley are testament to this fact. China would never want that India should become so powerful that it can challenge Chinese ambition in Asia. This is clear that India and America share same interest as far as rapidly increasing Chinese power is concerned. John Mearsheimer writes, in his famous book 'The Tragedy of Great Power Politics' that there is no such thing as status quo power in the world. A great power will not be satisfied until it attains the position of hegemony. This means that China will augment its power till it surpasses America. For avoiding this situation, America should pass on the responsibility of balancing China to India and then help India with full might so it can balance the rising China. In the parlance of international relations, it is called Buck Passing. India should accept this responsibility because India is the most threatened country from Chinese aggression. This is called Buck Catching. There are obvious geographical reasons behind this. There is a distance of 11, 640 kilometers between China and America. So, China definitely intends to replace America as the foremost power of the world but for America the danger is not imminent for the simple geographical reasons.

Mearsheimer also talks about the 'stopping power of water.' If there are great bodies of water between the two countries, it is difficult, but not impossible, to threaten each other. So due to geographical factors, danger for America is some time away. On the other hand, India and China share a boundary of 3,488 Kilometers. And to top it all, a China claims a big chunk of territory in India. After the Sumdorong Valley crisis in 1987, China has deliberately been creating new crises at repeated intervals to keep India at tenterhooks.

Theoretical Structure

As mentioned earlier, this paper is based upon the theory of aggressive realism presented by John Mearsheimer.

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Mearsheimer's theory of aggressive realism agrees with Morgenthau's realism but it suggests certain improvements to increase the explanatory power of realism. Basic tenets of aggressive realism are as follows—

1-States are the most important actors of international relations.

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2-International system is always in the state of anarchy because there is no universal hegemon to enforce rules, norms and treaties. Thus, international system becomes a self-help system. Every state has to take care of its problems itself.

3-If the states are asked to choose between morality and their own security, they will choose security over morality every time.

4-There is no such thing as status quo power in the international system. Every great power believes that best time for attaining hegemony is right now and right here. A great power believes that enemies should be crushed while they are weak. Once they become powerful, it will be difficult to subjugate them (Snyder, 2002).

5-There are occasions when in order to balance a rival, a great power transfers responsibility of doing that to a third power. This strategy is called Buck Passing.

6-The question is why that third country takes the responsibility of balancing the rival of the great power. The answer is that the third country is the most threatened one by the rival country. Thus, third country catches the buck and this strategy is called Buck Catching. Buck Catcher has the advantage of having full support of the Buck Passer. Generally, Buck Catcher shares the border with the rival whom Buck Passer wants to balance. The means Buck Catcher is the most threatened country by this rival.

Why There is a Need to Balance China?

Right now, China is the biggest threat to Westphalian international system. Chinese geographic borders coincide with many countries. China has a border dispute with every single country apart from Pakistan (BBC 2021). China is the only country which has friendly relations with North Korea and Iran, while whole world is maintaining a distance with these countries due to their nuclear ambitions. There is an extreme anger in Middle East due to Chinese nuclear deals with Iran. Similarly, South Korea and rest of the world is angered by Chinese nuclear relationship with North Korea. This is hardly a secret that it is due to China, that Pakistan was able to acquire nuclear weapons. Chinese activities are danger to nuclear non-proliferation regime of the world. The sophisticated missiles that are required to make a nuclear attack are also acquired by Pakistan from Chinese help (Mahapatra, 2021). Chinese activities in South China Sea are a danger to whole world. Without logic, China claims the minerals available in South China Sea as its own. Beijing also claims the Sea Lanes of Communications (SLOC) in the South China Sea (PTI 2021). China intends to take the advantage of poverty and acquire their natural resources. China is the only country in the world which forces websites like Wikipedia to show the definition of democracy which is in accordance with Chinese conception of the idea of democracy. China has been able to force companies like Goggle to follow its dictates. Manufacturing sector of the world is completely dominated by China. Since there is no democracy and rule of law, China is free to utilize child labor in the contravention to international norms and treaties. Since there is no concept of labor rights in China, cheap labor is freely available in China. This is the reason Chinese products are cheapest in the world. It is hardly surprising that China has the positive balance of trade with every single country it trades with. (Bagchi, 2019) Chinese government applies such monetary and trade policies which make sure that its products are cheapest in the world. The price for economic success has been paid by Chinese workers. China's ambitious One Belt One Road (OBOR) program is threat to world peace and security.

If seen from the lens of aggressive realism, China will never become a status quoist country. According to China, the best time for achieving global hegemony is right now. In order to attain hegemony, China has to replace America as the global hegemon. In order to secure its position of global hegemony, America has to adopt multi-pronged strategy to contain China. China's economic integration with America and at the same time strategic competition with America is referred to as Thucydides Embrace by global scholars. There are only two consequences to this situation. Either America should reconcile with the fact that it will become the second-grade power or China should accept the secondary position. The same situation exists between India and China in the Asian theater. China assumes that according to the theory of aggressive realism, it is only a matter of time when Indian will challenge the Chinese hegemony in Asia. In such scenario, Chinese options are very clear. China has to stop India before it matures as a great power and becomes a threat to China. Thus,

the interests of India and America are completely aligned. Both want to contain the rise of ascendent China.

Why China is a Threat for America?

There is hardly anyone who doubts that China will keep on increasing its power to the level that it will be able to replace America as the global hegemon. American strategists are fully aware of the situation. Christopher Wray, the chief of Federal Bureau of Investigation that there is no doubt that China is the future challenger to American dominance and in the game of strategy, America's global position is at the stake. Wray said, "China is doing everything to replace America. Things are so bad that FBI has to begin a new investigation every ten hours related to Chinese spying activities." Chinese intention is to influence American foreign policy by data theft, economic pressure, monetary policies, illegal political activities, bribe, blackmailing and lobbying. Globalization due to the spread of information technology and increasing importance of data and information have helped China in increasing direct and indirect power (Wray,2020). Donald Trump, former American President, was a staunch critic of Chinese policies. He accused China explicitly of spreading Corona virus. Trump even accused that China is trying to steal corona related data from American laboratories. Trump also accused China of taking advantage of open markets of America and increase its exports. But on the other hand, China imposes tariff and non-tariff barriers on American goods in its markets. (Bloomberg, 2021) Biden Administration disagrees with most of the policies of Trump, but trade war with China remains a common factor between the two administrations. America has accused that Chinese claims on South China Sea are completely fabricated. China wants to threaten the smaller countries situated around South China sea and capture the petroleum reserves in the region and dominate the sea lanes. A large portion of American trade passes through South China Sea. That's the reason that America is not willing to accept Chinese sovereignty over the South China Sea. American secretary of state has accused China of being the biggest threat to global peace and security. China has belligerently responded that actually it is America which is the biggest threat to world peace and security. China has accused that in last two decades, due to American policies in Afghanistan, Iraq, Syria and Libya, eight lakh people have died and millions have been displaced.

Why Should India Help America to Balance China?

There are strong geopolitical factors which prescribe that India should help America to contain the rise of ascendant China. As mentioned earlier, there is a distance of 11,640 kilometers between China and America while India shares long and treacherous boundary of 3,488 kilometers with China. This makes it clear that China is a threat to America in long term. But in short term, it is India which is the most threatened country from China. During 1950s, India-China relations were very cozy and the spirit of 'Indians and Chinese are brothers' dominated the bilateral relations. In order to improve relation even further, both countries propagated the five principles of peace and security, better known as 'Panchsheel'. But China had ulterior intentions. On the one hand, China was acting to be friends with India and on the other China was making elaborate plans to attack India. The way China attacked India in 1962, it is obvious that Beijing had been prepared for the intrusion for months. China captured thousands of kilometers of Indian land. After that, skirmishes on India-China border became regular events. In 1967, there were two skirmishes between India and China on Sikkim border. When India awarded full statehood to Sikkim, again war like conditions prevailed on border. In 1987, two armies again found themselves in front of each other on Sumdorong Valley and a major war was barely averted. In 2017, two armies again found themselves in fighting position in Doklam. Galwan crisis of 2020 carried on for months and it has still not been completely resolved. Apart from that the intervention in Indian border by Chinese Army has become a regular feature. Very frequently, Chinese soldiers intrude Indian boundary and with spray paint write 'China' on the rocks. These all skirmishes show a pattern. Chinese intention is to keep India always on tenterhooks. China wants that India should always feel insecure about its borders and should not think of challenging the rise of Chinese influence in Asia. As long as, India will remain insecure about its own border, no one will take India's claim seriously that it has emerged as a global power.

There are two other aspects to India-China relations. China has consistently supported Pakistan as a hedge against India. China has consistently ignored Pakistan sponsored terrorism in India. India is the only country which has fought wars with both of its neighbors. And interestingly, all three countries involved—India, China and Pakistan—form a nuclear triangle. There is no parallel to this triangle in the entire world. Thus, for India there is no rule book regarding how to handle two nuclear neighbors. Apart from this, China is the biggest trading partner of India. In 1988, Indian Prime Minister Rajiv Gandhi traveled to China and it was agreed that the border issue should be put on backburner and both countries should start working on economic relationship. China penetrated Indian markets with its cheap goods. In 2020, India-China trade was approximately 78 billion US \$. India's trade deficit was 40 billion US \$. This is a very worrying situation. Realist paradigm of international relations believe that trade could be strategically used by a country to influence the foreign policy of another country. A country might deliberately sell cheap goods in order to make another country dependent on it. Thus, both strategically and economically, China is in a position to threaten India.

Aggressive Realism and India's Foreign Policy Options

According to John Mearsheimer's theory of aggressive realism, India should understand that it is the most threatened country by China. (Chandra, 2020) As far as long term is concerned, America is the most threatened country by China. In such scenario, America wants to pass the responsibility of balancing China to India, which is the strategy of Buck Passing. If India accepts this responsibility by Buck Catching, it will have full might of America behind it to balance China. The logic here is that India is in any case compelled to face Chinese threat but if it catches the Buck passed by America then it will have the added advantage of American support to fend off China. Thus, it will be easier for India to repel Chinese advances. That is why, it is logical that due to geopolitical compulsions, America should adopt the strategy of Buck Passing and India should go for Buck Catching

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